

Bradford HDRC Policy Brief

Using Arts and Creativity to Improve health and wellbeing, education and social outcomes

Target Audience: Local Authorities

Based on N8 Child of the North Report - An evidence-based approach approach to creating a culture of inclusive opportunity through arts and creativity

CoTN_arts-creativity_Report.pdf

Key Evidence Based Messages

- Arts and creative education can have a transformative impact on children and young people and should be at the heart of education from primary school.
- It can improve CYPs health and wellbeing, cognitive, social and emotional development and can help increase school engagement, attendance and attainment. This is especially true for the most disadvantaged children.
- Creative industries are also key to the economy and arts and creative education can develop skills and pathways to employment.
- But 93% of children in state schools are excluded from arts and cultural education. The focus of the school curriculum is narrow, and many young people are disengaged.
- It is the poorest and most vulnerable children who are hardest hit and whose families can least afford to compensate for a lack of access to arts and creative education in schools.
- **National level focus:**
 - Place creativity and arts at the heart of the primary school curriculum. Embed creativity in all subjects as part of the Government's Opportunity Mission to support creative and vocational subjects in school.
 - Increase arts investment – create a £150m arts premium fund to support training and provision of programmes and double the Early Years Enrichment Fund.
 - Enrich education by connecting schools to cultural institutions. Support this with a Cultural Enrichment Fund.
- **Local level focus:**
 - Prioritise and advocate for the importance of arts and creative education for all pupils.
 - Create local partnerships with cultural institutions, artists and performers to provide a wide range of activities.
 - Develop enrichment opportunities for extracurricular activities for all pupils and year-round offers by providing programmes across holiday periods. Focus specifically on the most deprived areas.
 - Engage parents, CYP and local communities and work with them to design, develop and deliver local programmes.
 - Build on examples trialed in practice and featured in this briefing.

The Problem: Due to lack of funding, 93% of children in state schools are excluded from arts and cultural education. The curriculum is narrow. Many young people, especially those from the most disadvantaged and vulnerable backgrounds fail to engage, attain and reach their potential. But arts and creativity education can have transformative impacts on CYPs health and wellbeing and engagement and attainment in education. The creative industries are also vital to the economy and offer access to careers and opportunities, but these are currently denied to all but the most privileged.

42% of schools no longer enter pupils for GCSE Maths
41% no longer enter pupils for GCSE drama
84% do not offer GCSE dance

Engaging in the arts can provide up to 3 months of academic progress in English, Maths and Science

Participation in extracurricular activities decreased from 46% pre pandemic to 37% post pandemic

In 2022, creative industries employed 2.4 million people and added £31 billion in gross added value to UK economy

86% of Interns in creative industries are unpaid and just 8% of workers in TV and radio are from working class backgrounds

What you can do at a local level

- Prioritise and advocate for the importance of arts, play and creative education to be at the heart of the school curriculum.
- Develop local strategies and partnerships to foster the development of arts and creative education and set locally based approaches that reflect the diversity of local communities. But integrate these with a wider strategic, whole systems approach to tackling systemic problems. For example, programmes such as the Educational Alliance for Life Chances in Bradford are doing this.
- Work with schools to place arts and creative education at the heart of the school curriculum. Support schools in developing place-based partnerships with cultural institutions, Higher Education Institutions, employers, artists and performers to build local capacity and opportunities.
- Work creatively with partners to bring arts and culture into the school curriculum and to take the school curriculum out to arts and cultural venues and draw on the natural environment, for example through forest education for young children or science classes in secondary school.
- Develop programmes of extracurricular enrichment activities, especially in the most disadvantaged areas where children have least access to sports, music, arts and cultural enrichment opportunities.
- Work with partners to develop programmes of arts, sports and creative activities over holiday periods and explore the potential of using local assets such as parks, the natural environment and museums to develop a “year-round” offer for children and young people.
- Work with parents and communities and harness their potential to develop, design and deliver programmes.
- Build on the approaches trialed in practice and featured below.

Approaches trialed in practice

Example	Approach	Impact
Hands of Charity	Provides creative opportunities for disadvantaged CYP to work with professionals to create live performances, films, sound walks, art exhibitions, which are authentically the CYPs creations and reflect their voices.	School data shows improvements in attainment, attendance, attitude to learning and independent learning and homework routines.
Morecambe Bay Curriculum (supported by Lancaster University, Lancaster and Morecambe College, University of Cumbria and the Eden Project)	Educator-led movement and a cross-sector partnership that embeds creativity, sustainability and place-based learning. It works on three fundamentals: integrating arts into curriculum design; enhancing teacher training in art practice, utilising co-design methods for place-based learning. Aims to integrate Head (knowledge), Heart (values) and Hands (skills) through its programmes.	Through place-based education promoting understanding of sustainability and developing young people as agents of change, the programme aims to impact on mental/physical health, work and the local economy and people and local community. There are currently 234 members of the MBC movement. Resources are shared with 300 schools and colleges and 100 early years settings.
Theatre Hullabaloo, Play on Prescription and Place to Play	The Theatre Hullabaloo charity has designed a creativity space housing a rolling programme of artist designed early years play environments. These are free. Play on Prescription prescribes creative play interventions for 0-3 year olds and their carers. Places to Play builds on the creativity space to work in partnership with public health and the Combined Authority in South Tees to create play spaces in Family Hubs.	Through providing access to creative play and activity sessions, particularly for the most disadvantaged families, the programmes aim to boost the cognitive, social and emotional development of children and provide support to parents and carers and connect parents and children with local support services.

Example	Approach	Impact
Mortal Fools	Northumberland based project which works with young people to promote inclusion through the arts and break down barriers to access. The majority of young people have complex needs. Young people, artists and communities work together to produce a range of theatre, film and creative projects.	Aims to provide access to arts and creative education programmes and develop the resilience, confidence and independence of young people. The programme works with some of the most vulnerable young people: severe deprivation, looked after children, those at risk of suicide and self-harm and is showing real improvement in the wellbeing of these young people.
Echoes of Resilience: Refugee Voices in Art	Project which uses art to provide a safe platform and environment to provide the refugee community in a northern town with a means of expression and voice. The programme provides tailored curriculum workshops for participants aged 10-50, held at the local museum community gallery.	The project produced an exhibition and has led to development of further classes and creation of pathways to further education and qualifications in the arts. Participants of the project reported improvements in emotional wellbeing and confidence in their own abilities. The project was well received by the wider community and made previously hidden narratives visible.
Helix Art	A charity which works with local communities across the North East. It uses a range of art forms such as dance, music, film and drama in a wide range of settings e.g., schools, youth centers, care homes, hospitals, prisons. For CYP, arts are used to champion voice and foster social agency.	The charity aims to use arts, cultural and historical projects to develop the agency and voice of CYP and create a renewed sense of community. It aims to break down social barriers to arts involvement and foster inclusion and social justice.
Middlesborough Institute of Modern Art (MIMA) – Teeside University.	MIMA brings together art, people and ideas to make a creative community space. It serves as a cultural and community hub promoting public engagement underpinned by equity, diversity and inclusion. It aims to transform art into action and runs a wider range of artistic and learning programmes including Philosophy for Children events, support for schools in achieving national accreditation Arts Awards, early years programmes and programmes that focus on specific issues such as holiday hunger.	Each year over 12000 school children experience MIMA through visits and the Philosophy for Children method is used to invite speculation, reflection and imagination. Work with specific schools aims to increase confidence, improve wellbeing and improve communication skills.
Beyond School Gates: Children's Contribution to Community Integration.	Research project funded by the British Academy and Nuffield Foundation looking at how children's experiences, interactions, and friendships networks feed into community integration. in 3 northern towns.	The research showed the importance of arts-based methods for story telling. It also found that there needs to be a policy with a clear vision for working with children ages 5-12.